

Enhancement of dielectric properties of nanocomposite thin films prepared from polyimide and nickel doped barium titanate ceramic

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Manuscript received 10 January 2018, revised 12 February 2018, accepted 15 February 2018

Abstract : Nickel doped barium titanate ceramics, $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$ (where $x = 0.0, 0.01, 0.03$ and 0.05) were synthesized by using sol-gel method and their dielectric properties were evaluated. In this manuscript the effect of Ni doping on its structural and dielectric properties were explained. It was observed that the crystal structure of the synthesized ceramics was decided by the amount of Ni present in the ceramic. A very small amount of Ni has the capacity to increase the dielectric constant value of $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$. Among the synthesized ceramics, $\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ (BNT) showed the highest dielectric constant, 9281 at 1 Hz frequency. A series of BNT/polyimide (BNT/PI) nanocomposite films were prepared by varying the weight percentage of BNT (0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 wt%) in PI matrix. The obtained nanocomposite films were characterized thoroughly. The prepared films showed high glass transition temperature up to 304°C with high thermal stability up to 568°C at 10% weight loss in nitrogen atmosphere. Mechanical properties of the polymer composite films were also evaluated. In sacrifice of the smaller amount of mechanical strength, an increase in thermal and dielectric properties were achieved. The nanocomposite films also display a good dielectric stability over the frequency range of 1 Hz to 1 MHz. The highest dielectric constant 18.42 was obtained for 5 wt% BNT loading in the nanocomposite film.

Keywords : Nickel doped barium titanate, polyimide, nanocomposite, mechanical property, dielectric constant.

Introduction

In recent years, a variety of polymer-ceramic nanocomposites have been used for microelectronic devices, packaging material, telecommunication and medical applications¹. A large number of polymer matrices such as polybenzoxazole, epoxy, cyanate ester, polystyrene, polyethylene and polyimide with inorganic (ceramic) fillers have been studied for composite preparation². Among the polymers, aromatic polyimide is one of the most important polymers, which is used in microelectronic industries because of their easy machinability, flexibility, low cost, good resistance towards many organic solvents and high tensile strength³. Polyimide is an aromatic organic material which shows certain limitations for much higher performance functions in which ceramic (inorganic) materials are used as fillers. Whereas ceramic particles exhibit excellent thermal stability,

high dielectric constant and low dissipation factor with bad film forming property and high brittleness. To improve the properties of both organic and inorganic materials, polymer-ceramic composites were prepared⁴. The flexible composite materials in circuits have the ability to withstand high level of strain without loss of electronic properties. The physical and chemical properties of composite materials not only depend on the properties of the parent polymer and ceramic materials but also on the volume fraction, morphology and connectivity of the phases⁵. The addition of small inorganic nanocrystal fillers (with a size less than 300 nm) into organic compound (polymer) can increase the interfacial surface area which helps to produce smoother, defect free and thin composite films with good mechanical properties⁶. Larger micrometer sized inorganic fillers provides lower active surface areas and produce a

thicker and more rough films⁷. Many researchers studied about the synthesis and characterization of barium titanate and doped barium titanate, which were used in composite preparation.

Das *et al.* studied the electrical properties of Ni doped barium titanate ceramic. They synthesized $\text{BaTi}_{1-x}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$ (where $x = 0.05, 0.1$ and 0.15) through solid state sintering method. It was reported that the phase transformation of Ni doped barium titanate was strongly influenced by Ni doping concentration. They observed that at room temperature the electrical properties was decreased by Ni doping⁸. Renzhengchen *et al.* reported that the effect of Ni metal on the dielectric properties of Ni-BaTiO₃ composite. The dielectric constant increased with Ni-content. A very high dielectric constant was observed with 28 vol% of Ni content and at 30 vol% the composite became a conductor⁹. Yogeswarkumar *et al.* synthesized a series of Ni doped barium titanate ($\text{Ba}_{1-x}\text{Ni}_x\text{TiO}_3$ where $x = 0.0, 0.03, 0.05, 0.07$ and 0.10) by solid state reaction technique. They studied crystalline structure of the doped barium titanate, which affect its dielectric constant and the value decreases with increase in nickel ion concentration¹⁰. Kundu *et al.* had reported the synthesis of Ni doped barium titanate $\text{BaTi}_{1-z}\text{Ni}_z\text{O}_3$ where $z = 0.03, 0.06, 0.1, 0.16$ and 0.2 . The dielectric behavior was explained in terms of crystalline structure of the prepared specimens. Nickel doped barium titanate showed higher dielectric constant than pure barium titanate. They reported the highest dielectric constant value for the composition which having maximum c/a (lattice parameter) ratio¹¹. Here we observed that cubic to tetragonal phase change occurred with the addition of nickel ion and the tetragonality decreases with increase in the concentration of nickel ion on barium titanate. We have also reported a relationship between dielectric constant and tetragonality i.e. more the tetragonality or c/a ratio (lattice parameters), more will be the dielectric constant value.

In this paper, we studied the dielectric properties of nickel doped barium titanate ceramics and

nanocomposite films containing BNT and polyimide. Firstly, $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles were synthesized with different stoichiometric ratio (where $x = 0.0, 0.01, 0.03$ and 0.05) and characterized thoroughly. The dielectric properties of the Ni doped barium titanate were studied to evaluate the effect of Ni doping and correlate the properties with their structure. Nanocomposite films were prepared with the highest achieved dielectric ceramic, $\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$. The nanocomposite films were prepared by solution casting method, where suspension of well-defined nanocrystals of BNT in dimethylacetamide (DMAc) mixed with the solution of 4,4'-oxydianiline (ODA) and pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA) in DMAc solvent with different ceramic loading percentage (1%, 2%, 3%, 4% and 5%). The resulting nanocomposite films were characterized by FTIR, XRD, SEM, AFM etc. Thermal, mechanical and dielectric properties of the films were also evaluated and compared with the pure polyimide films. From the impedance analysis, we have reported that BNT ceramic filler increases the dielectric constant of the nanocomposite films as compared to the pure polyimide.

Experimental

Materials :

Nickel doped barium titanate ceramic were synthesized by using barium acetate (99.5%, AnalaR, A.R.), nickel nitrate hexahydrate (98%, Rankem) and titanium(IV) isopropoxide (98%, ACROS Organics) as the starting material. Acetic acid (99.5%, Fisher Scientific) was used as a solvent for the reaction. Before addition of titanium(IV) isopropoxide to the reaction mixture it was added to 2-methoxyethanol (99%, Spectrochem, A.R.) to avoid any precipitation of titanium compound. Ethylene glycol (98%, Qualigens Fine Chemicals) was used for the complete dissolution of the starting materials. For the preparation of nanocomposite thin film PMDA (Sigma-Aldrich, 97% purity), ODA (Spectrochem, 98% purity), DMAc (Spectrochem, 99% purity) and synthesized BNT nanoparticles were used. PMDA

and ODA were heated in a vacuum oven prior to use to remove moisture from it and DMAc was stirred by adding calcium hydride powder overnight and then distilled. The distilled DMAc solvent was store in 4 Å molecular sieves for further use.

Synthesis procedure :

Synthesis of BaTi_(1-x)Ni_xO₃ ceramic :

The steps for the synthesis of BaTi_(1-x)Ni_xO₃ where x = 0.0, 0.01, 0.03 and 0.05, is represented in Fig. 1(a). Nickel doped barium titanate were synthesized by sol-gel method. Calculated amount of barium acetate and nickel nitrate hexahydrate were dissolved in acetic acid and then both the solution were mixed together after that it was refluxed for 3 h at 60°C, then ethylene glycol was added to the mixed solution for complete dissolution of the reactants. On the other hand titanium isopropoxide was added to 2-methoxyethanol to avoid the formation of precipitate of titanium compound and then it was mixed with the solution of barium and nickel compound, which

forms sol phase. Here, 2-methoxy-ethanol was used as a stabilizing agent. Sol-phase was again reflux for 2 h which form gel-phase. The obtained gel was evaporated to get the powder form of ceramic and then it was dried in an oven at 60°C for 12 h. The obtained powder was grinded in an agate mortar pestle and calcined for 2 h at 700°C in a muffle furnace.

Synthesis of BNT/PI nanocomposites :

A schematic representation for the preparation of BNT/PI nanocomposite films is shown in Fig. 1(b). The synthesized BaTi_{0.99}Ni_{0.01}O₃ was used for the preparation of nanocomposite film. Measured quantity of synthesized BNT powder was mixed in DMAc solvent and sonicated in a probe sonicator for 2 h to form suspension of the ceramic. The suspension was mixed with poly(amic)acid solution which was prepared by mixing solution of ODA in DMAc solvent with an equimolar amount of PMDA. For the complete dispersion of ceramic nanoparticles into the poly(amic)acid solution, the mixture was ultrasoni-

Fig. 1. A schematic representation for preparation of (a) BaTi_(1-x)Ni_xO₃ nanoparticles and (b) BNT/PI nanocomposite film.

cated and then cast on a dust free petridish. To remove the solvent, it was heated overnight at 80°C and for complete thermal imidization the film was heated in an oven at 100, 120, 150, 200 and 220°C each for 1 h. The synthesized nanocomposite films were in the range of 0.03–0.05 mm thickness.

Characterization :

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra of the synthesized ceramic were obtained by scanning from 4000–400 cm^{-1} by using IR-Prestige-21, Shimadzu made in Japan. X-Ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed by using Rigaku MiniFlex600 with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.541 \text{ \AA}$) radiation, at a scanning rate of 3° min^{-1} . Glass transition temperature of the composite films was measured by Differential Scanning Calorimetric (DSC) (TA Instruments, USA, Q10) study. Thermal stability of the composite films were analyzed by using a thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA) (Shimadzu, Japan, DTG-60) at a heating rate of $10^\circ \text{C min}^{-1}$. Surface morphology of the ceramics and the composite films was examined by SEM (Jeol, Japan, JSM-6390LV) and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) (NT-MDT, Russia, Solver Pro-47). Instrument, Instron Corporation Series IX, was used for the study of tensile strength of the composite films. Impedance analyzer (Novocontrol ALPHA ATB) was used for the dielectric measurement of the sample, in the frequency range of 1 Hz to 1 MHz. For this a pellet of thickness 1 mm and diameter 10 mm was prepared for each sample of ceramic and then sintered at 1000°C for 2 h to increase the mechanical strength. Sintered ceramic pellets and nanocomposite films were coated with silver paste on both the sides and then capacitance measurement was done by the instrument. The obtained capacitance values were used for the calculation of dielectric constant and it was calculated by using the formula,

$$K = C t / \epsilon_0 A$$

where, K = dielectric constant, C = capacitance, t = thickness, ϵ_0 = permittivity of free space ($8.85 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F/m}$) and A = area of the sintered pellet.

Results and discussion

Result and discussion of $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$:

Structural analysis :

In the FTIR spectrum, a broad absorption band in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} suggests the formation of Ni doped barium titanate¹². Fig. S1 indicates the FTIR spectrum of Ni doped barium titanate nanoparticles, synthesized at 700°C for 2 h. The stretching vibration of hydroxyl group is assigned by the absorption band at 3400 cm^{-1} . The presence of hydroxyl group in the prepared nanoparticles was expected due to the use of KBr as a binder, which is a moisture sensitive material. A broad absorption band at around 540 cm^{-1} was observed, which represents the stretching vibration of Ti-O bond from perovskite phase structure¹³. The presence of acetate group bonded to barium atoms was confirmed by two bands near 1400 cm^{-1} and 1750 cm^{-1} which is due to symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations of carboxylate group respectively¹⁴. FTIR spectrum of the nickel doped barium titanate confirmed the presence of functional group in perovskite structure of the obtained nanoparticles.

The formation of well-developed crystals of synthesized ceramic samples were confirmed by XRD analysis. X-Ray crystallography study was used to determine the degree of tetragonality and lattice parameter values of undoped and nickel doped barium titanate. Fig. 2 shows the room temperature XRD patterns of the synthesized nanoparticles. The major peaks could be indexed perovskite tetragonal phase for the undoped barium titanate and the nickel doped barium titanate ceramics. No any secondary peaks were observed in the XRD pattern of the synthesized nanoparticles i.e. all the samples were in single phase. The XRD pattern of undoped and nickel doped barium titanate were matched with the JCPDS card no. 81-2203. All the synthesized ceramics showed eight peaks with miller indices (0 0 1), (1 0 1), (1 1 1), (2 0 0), (1 0 2), (2 0 1), (2 1 1) and (2 0 2) which confirmed the tetragonal phase of the nanoparticles having space group P4mm in the range of 20–70° diffraction angle.

Smaller Ni²⁺ ion in comparison to Ba²⁺ ions shifted the XRD peaks towards lower 2θ values with respect to the undoped barium titanate. XRD data of the Ni doped barium titanate has concluded that all the major peaks matched with the reported data of the undoped barium titanate in tetragonal phase, which showed nickel doping is perfect. It confirmed that all the synthesized Ni doped barium titanate nanoparticles exhibited tetragonal phase. The crystallite size of the nanoparticles was calculated from the XRD line broadening using the Scherrer's relationship $D = 0.9\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$, where D is the crystallite size, β is the full width at half maxima of the peak, θ is half the value of diffraction angle and λ is the wavelength of X-rays. Here in our instrument the wavelength of the CuK_α-radiation was 1.54 Å. The calculated average particle size for BaTiO₃, BaTi_{0.99}Ni_{0.01}O₃, BaTi_{0.97}Ni_{0.03}O₃ and BaTi_{0.95}Ni_{0.05}O₃ were 17.11, 30.01, 29.78 and 27.93 nm respectively. From the obtained value we have observed that nickel doping on barium titanate increases the particle size of the ceramic and the size decreases with increase in the value of x . Table 1

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of BaTi_(1-x)Ni_xO₃ nanoparticles calcined at 700 °C for 2 h.

Table 1. hkl , θ , β and D (grain size) value of the obtained BaTiO₃ and Ni doped BaTiO₃ nanoparticle

hkl	BaTiO ₃			BaTi _{0.99} Ni _{0.01} O ₃			BaTi _{0.97} Ni _{0.03} O ₃			BaTi _{0.95} Ni _{0.05} O ₃		
	θ	β (radian)	D (nm)	θ	β (radian)	D (nm)	θ	β (radian)	D (nm)	θ	β (radian)	D (nm)
0 0 1	11.05	6.50×10^{-3}	24.14	11.14	4.65×10^{-3}	33.77	11.05	4.62×10^{-3}	33.99	11.08	4.64×10^{-3}	33.84
1 0 1	15.89	8.11×10^{-3}	19.76	15.77	4.79×10^{-3}	33.40	15.74	4.98×10^{-3}	32.15	15.70	4.94×10^{-3}	32.42
1 1 1	19.45	9.52×10^{-3}	17.16	19.49	4.91×10^{-3}	33.33	19.44	4.73×10^{-3}	34.60	19.35	8.10×10^{-3}	20.26
2 0 0	22.94	1.15×10^{-2}	14.66	22.64	6.41×10^{-3}	26.35	22.60	6.31×10^{-3}	26.46	22.64	6.13×10^{-3}	27.25
1 0 2	25.15	7.16×10^{-3}	23.22	24.77	6.01×10^{-3}	28.25	24.74	6.61×10^{-3}	25.65	24.73	6.63×10^{-3}	25.57
2 0 1	25.64	1.07×10^{-2}	15.97	25.46	5.80×10^{-3}	29.44	25.44	5.51×10^{-3}	30.98	25.44	5.68×10^{-3}	30.07
2 1 1	28.35	1.42×10^{-2}	10.92	28.10	6.40×10^{-3}	27.50	28.07	6.27×10^{-3}	27.84	27.96	6.32×10^{-3}	27.59
2 0 2	32.97	1.66×10^{-2}	11.11	32.89	6.54×10^{-3}	28.05	32.87	6.89×10^{-3}	26.64	32.87	6.92×10^{-3}	26.50

The average crystallite size of the BaTiO₃, BaTi_{0.99}Ni_{0.01}O₃, BaTi_{0.97}Ni_{0.03}O₃, BaTi_{0.95}Ni_{0.05}O₃ nanoparticles are 17.11, 30.01, 29.78 and 27.93 nm respectively.

Table 2. Lattice parameter of $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$

BaTiO_3	$\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$	$\text{BaTi}_{0.97}\text{Ni}_{0.03}\text{O}_3$	$\text{BaTi}_{0.95}\text{Ni}_{0.05}\text{O}_3$
$a = 3.9941 \text{ \AA}$	$a = 4.0114 \text{ \AA}$	$a = 4.0071 \text{ \AA}$	$a = 3.9869 \text{ \AA}$
$c = 4.0021 \text{ \AA}$	$c = 4.0351 \text{ \AA}$	$c = 4.0243 \text{ \AA}$	$c = 4.0014 \text{ \AA}$
$c/a = 1.0025$	$c/a = 1.0059$	$c/a = 1.0042$	$c/a = 1.0036$

showed the hkl value, θ , β and D (grain size) of the obtained undoped barium titanate and Ni doped barium titanate nanoparticles. The lattice parameters of the synthesized samples were calculated by using software X-pert highscore plus. Table 2 represents the lattice parameter values of the nanoparticles. In all the cases the value of c axis is greater than the a axis, which supported the formation of tetragonal structure of the ceramic nanoparticles.

Surface morphology :

Surface morphology and the grain size of the sintered sample were observed by SEM images of the nanoparticles. One of the representative SEM and EDX graph of the sintered nickel doped barium titanate nanoparticle is represented in Fig. 3. From the SEM micrographs it was clear that the uniform grains were develop in the sintered sample. We have observed that the size of the particles were in the range of 241–261 nm for the sintered $\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ nanoparticle. EDX graph confirmed the presence of Ba, Ti, Ni and O elements in the prepared sample of $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$.

Dielectric properties :

Frequency dependence dielectric constant was calculated in the range of 1 Hz to 1 MHz. Fig. 4(a) shows the variation of dielectric constant value with respect to the frequency. We have observed that in $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$ ceramic the dielectric constant varied by changing the ratio of Ni to Ti. In comparison to the barium titanate higher value of dielectric constant was obtained for the Ni doped barium titanate. The calculated dielectric constant for BaTiO_3 , $\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$, $\text{BaTi}_{0.97}\text{Ni}_{0.03}\text{O}_3$ and $\text{BaTi}_{0.95}\text{Ni}_{0.05}\text{O}_3$ was 1175, 9281, 5485 and 2006 respectively at 1 Hz frequency. It was observed that dielectric constant decreases with the increase in the concentration of Ni in $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$. Here the variation of dielectric constant explained in terms of change in lattice parameter value (c/a) of the synthesized ceramic nanoparticles. The result indicated that very small amount of nickel doping ($x = 0.01$) on barium titanate increases the dielectric constant of the doped barium titanate, but the value decreases with the increase in the value of x ($x > 0.01$). The highest c/a value was obtained for nickel doped barium titanate

Fig. 3. EDX and SEM image of $\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles sintered at 1000°C for 2 h.

with $x = 0.01$, and the ratio decreases with the increase in the value of x i.e. the tetragonality decreases with the increase in the doping percentage of nickel, which results lower value of dielectric constant. For all the prepared nanoparticles, higher dielectric constant value was obtained in lower frequency region because in this region different types of polarization acts (atomic, ionic, interfacial, electronic polarization), but only electronic polarization affects the value in the higher frequency region.

Like dielectric constant, dielectric loss value also decreases with the increase in frequency for all the ceramic samples because at higher frequency region dipole contributes to the polarization. This type of trend was also reported in various paper¹⁵. Fig. 4(b) represents the variation of dielectric loss ($\tan \delta$) with frequency. The dielectric loss value was directly related to the imaginary part of the dielectric constant. The higher $\tan \delta$ value was obtained for Ni doped barium titanate in comparison with undoped barium titanate and the value increases with the value of x . Among the series of Ni doped barium titanate, the lowest dielectric loss was obtained for $\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$. Due to high dielectric constant value 9281 and low dielectric loss 2.49 at 1 Hz frequency, $\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ was chosen as ceramic filler for the preparation of nanocomposite thin film.

Result and discussion of BNT/PI nanocomposites :

Preparation of the composites :

Fig. 5 represents the FTIR graph of the prepared nanocomposite films. Two absorption peaks at $\sim 1767\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1717\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicated that there was asymmetry and symmetric stretching vibration of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bonding respectively, these bands confirms the complete thermal imidization of the synthesized nanocomposite films containing polyimide. Another absorption peak for carbonyl group was observed at $\sim 715\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which was due to bending vibration^{6c}. The presence of C-N bonding in BNT/PI nanocomposite films were confirmed by absorption peak at $\sim 1365\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A peak at $\sim 1005\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicated

Fig. 4. Frequency dependent dielectric properties of $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles : (a) dielectric constant value and (b) $\tan \delta$.

Fig. 5. FTIR spectrum of BNT/PI nanocomposites.

the C-O-C bonding of the nanocomposite film. These peaks confirmed the presence of functional group in the nanocomposite film. The FTIR spectra of the BNT/PI nanocomposite were nearly the same as that of PI. This indicates that BNT/PI nanocomposite films have been successfully synthesized by solution casting method¹⁶. As we have already discussed that Ti-O stretching vibration of perovskite phase was observed at around 540 cm^{-1} , so it was not observed in the ATR mode of FTIR spectra of nanocomposite film.

Fig. S2 shows the XRD pattern of the prepared nanocomposite thin films. This confirmed the amorphous nature of the pure polyimide and BNT/PI nanocomposite films because here no sharp peak was observed. XRD of pure PI showed a broad peak centered at 19° and also small peaks at $2\theta = 31.54, 38.98, 50.92$ and 56.12° indicated the presence of BNT nanoparticles in the nanocomposite films. The absence of well-defined crystallinity was due to very less weight percentage (0–5 wt%) of BNT nanoparticles in the composite film whereas XRD peaks of BNT nanoparticles confirmed that it exhibit tetragonal structure.

Thermal properties :

The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the nanocomposite films were obtained by DSC study. It was carried out under nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The centre of the step transition in the second heating run indicates the T_g point. A DSC plot of the prepared PI and BNT/PI nanocomposite films is shown in Fig. 6. The glass transition temperatures were observed in the range of $251\text{--}304^\circ\text{C}$. The DSC plot supports the XRD result of the synthesized nanocomposite film, because no any crystallisation temperature was observed upto 350°C , which confirmed the amorphous nature of the nanocomposite films. All the nanocomposite series showed high glass transition temperature and the values increased with the increase in weight percentage of BNT ceramic in the composite film. This may

Fig. 6. DSC curves of BNT/PI nanocomposites.

be due to the high thermal stability of the ceramic.

The thermal stability of the synthesized nanocomposite films were investigated in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Fig. 7 represents the TGA graph of the nanocomposite films, which showed that loading of BNT ceramic particles in the polyimide film had positive effect on its thermal stability and the stability increased with the increase in weight percentage of the BNT content. The temperature at 10% wt loss were $484, 496, 505, 513, 517$ and 568°C for pure PI and BNT/PI nanocomposite films with 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 wt% re-

Fig. 7. TGA thermogram of BNT/PI nanocomposites.

Table 3. Thermal, mechanical, average roughness and dielectric properties of BNT/PI nanocomposites

Nanocomposite films	T_g (°C)	Temperature at 10% wt. loss (°C)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	% Elongation	Dielectric constant at 1 Hz	Dielectric loss at 1 Hz	Average roughness (nm)
Pure PI	251	484	111±9	4.5±0.33	12.1±0.37	3.23	0.77	26.77
1% BNT/PI	257	496	102±6	4.2±0.35	10.7±0.36	8.5	0.03	34.28
2% BNT/PI	276	505	97±8	3.7±0.38	8.3±0.41	8.72	0.09	38.61
3% BNT/PI	281	513	90±5	3.3±0.31	6.9±0.38	13.66	0.53	47.99
4% BNT/PI	298	517	85±9	3.0±0.44	5.7±0.33	16.12	1.90	58.76
5% BNT/PI	304	568	81±7	2.7±0.47	4.4±0.35	18.42	1.93	71.13

spectively. Table 3 summarized the thermal and mechanical properties of the prepared nanocomposite films.

Mechanical properties :

The flexibility is a very important requirement for a material which is supposed to be used for electrical applications. The prepared nanocomposite films were flexible with good mechanical strength. And the mechanical properties of polyimide showed a decreasing trend with the addition of ceramic particles, this was because of brittle nature of the ceramic particles. The tensile strength value for 5 wt% of BNT ceramic in the prepared nanocomposite film was observed to be 81 MPa with 4.4% elongation.

Surface morphology :

The morphology of the nanocomposite films were measured by SEM images which is shown in Fig. S3. It could be seen that BNT nanoparticles were uniformly distributed in the polyimide matrix. There was no aggregation of the nanoparticles in the composite films. The low weight percentage of the BNT nanoparticles in the composite film did not show much change in the morphology of the composite film. Surface morphology of the nanocomposite films were also studied by AFM. One of the representative 2D and 3D images of the BNT/PI film is shown in Fig. 8. It was observed that the roughness increases with the increase in BNT content in the film. The roughnesses of the films were ranges from 26.77–71.13 nm.

Fig. 8. AFM images of 5 wt% BNT/PI nanocomposite film: (a) 2D image and (b) 3D image.

Dielectric properties :

The filler nanoparticles not only affected thermal and mechanical property but also responsible for the dielectric properties of the composite film¹⁷. The dielectric constant and dissipation factor of the prepared BNT/PI nanocomposite films were measured in the frequency range of 1 Hz to 1 MHz. The prepared nanocomposite films exhibited excellent dielec-

tric property over this frequency range. The dielectric constant values of composite films were increased by increasing the BNT content from 0–5 wt% in the films over all the measured frequency range. Dielectric constant value was increased from 3.23 (for pure polyimide) to 18.42 (for 5 wt% BNT/PI) at 1 Hz frequency. Fig. 9(a) showed the variation of dielectric constant value with the frequency. In each case of the BNT nanocrystal loading, the dielectric loss decreases with the increase in frequency and the value remained below 0.03 over the frequency range of 1 kHz to 1 MHz. This type of variation was observed in different papers in lower frequency region^{6c,18,19}. The variation of dielectric loss with frequency is represented in Fig. 9(b). The dielectric properties of nanocomposite films were due to the dipole relaxation phenomenon. Dipole relaxation of the

nanocomposite films lag behind the change of applied fields¹⁸.

Conclusions

Nanocrystals of undoped and nickel doped barium titanate were synthesized by low temperature sol-gel method and their dielectric properties were investigated as a function of different concentration of nickel. XRD result revealed that all the synthesized ceramic samples were in tetragonal phase. The tetragonality was strongly influenced by the presence of Ni ion concentration in the synthesized ceramics. The lower c/a ratio was obtained for the higher Ni ion concentration in the synthesized ceramics i.e. the tetragonality decreased with increase in Ni ion concentration. The highest dielectric constant value (9281) was obtained for the composition $\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$, therefore it was opted for the preparation of nanocomposite films. A series of composite films containing 0–5 wt% of $\text{BaTi}_{0.99}\text{Ni}_{0.01}\text{O}_3$ ceramic were successfully prepared by solution casting method and characterize by different techniques. The BNT nanoparticles were homogeneously dispersed in the polyimide matrix without any agglomeration. The incorporation of BNT ceramic particles in the polyimide matrix led to increment of thermal stability of the nanocomposite films. More importantly, the dielectric constant was increases with increase in weight percent of ceramic fillers and it was almost constant throughout the long frequency range 1 Hz to 1 MHz. Nanocomposite film with 5 wt% BNT particles displayed a high dielectric constant of 18.42 which was about 5.7 times of 3.23 for pure polyimide. All the nanocomposites showed very good dielectric stability over all the measured frequency range. BNT/PI nanocomposite films should be a good candidate for electronic purposes where high dielectric materials are used.

Fig. 9. Frequency dependent dielectric properties of BNT/PI nanocomposites : (a) dielectric constant value and (b) $\tan \delta$.

Supporting Information

FTIR spectra of Ni doped barium titanate nanoparticles, XRD pattern of the prepared BNT/PI nanocomposite films and SEM micrograph of the nanocomposite film.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank to Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB), Department of Science and Technology (DST), Government of India for financial support in terms of a sponsored project (Sanction Order No. SB/FT/CS-194/2013) to carry out this work. The authors are grateful to the Department of Physics, Ranchi University, Ranchi and Central Instrumental Research Facility (CIF), Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra, Ranchi, India for providing the necessary facilities.

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